

**PREVALENCE OF WORK-RELATED STRESS AND ITS DETERMINANTS AMONG
HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN SELECTED HEALTH CARE FACILITIES IN
FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY, ABUJA, NIGERIA**

BY

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this research is my original work and has not been submitted, in part or in full, for any academic or professional qualification. I affirm that all sources used in this research have been appropriately acknowledged and cited. Any assistance received during the research process is duly acknowledged in the acknowledgment section of this work.

I am fully aware of and acknowledge the ethical considerations inherent in research endeavors, and I have adhered to all relevant guidelines and protocols. This research represents a genuine effort to contribute to the field of healthcare, and I take full responsibility for its content.

DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to Almighty God for His grace, favor and love upon my life throughout the period of my study and also for the success of this project.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Foremost, I express my gratitude to God Almighty for granting me health, fortitude, and wisdom to persevere in my studies, even during seemingly insurmountable challenges. I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my husband Mr. Richard Joel-Utulu, my mother Mrs. Faith Orunwebho, Dr. Umar Yahaya and Mr. Praise Olives whose assistance was essential to finishing this dissertation. This accomplishment would not have been achieved without their help and steadfast support.

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Abstract

Background: Work-related stress is a pervasive global issue, costing an estimated \$5.4 billion annually. Despite healthcare settings being recognized as high-risk environments, there's a dearth of data on the extent of work-related stress among workers in Nigeria. This study seeks to uncover the prevalence, sources, and determinants of work-related stress in selected healthcare facilities in FCT Abuja, specifically focusing on the experiences of nurses, medical doctors, laboratory scientists, and pharmacists.

Methods: This was an institution-based cross-sectional study across three public hospitals in Wuse, Maitama, and Garki in Abuja Municipal Area Council of FCT, Nigeria. A self-administered questionnaire based on the Health and Safety Executive's standards was used for data collection. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Percentage calculations and multinomial regression was employed to assess the determinants of work-related stress.

Results: Stress levels were categorized as high, neutral, or low within various sectors of the healthcare industry. The Role domain revealed a substantial 66.7% prevalence of high stress, with significant levels also observed in the Demand, Relationship, Support, Change, and Control domains (67.7%, 62.7%, 58.3%, 54.4%, 57.8% respectively). Profession-specific stress levels indicated unanimous agreement among doctors (100%), 90.2% agreement among nurses, 98% among laboratory scientists, and 78.4% among pharmacists. The study identified key predictors of work-related stress, including interpersonal conflict (87.3%), traumatic events such as workplace deaths (87.7%), heavy workloads (96.1%), uncooperative patients and their families (87.8%), and uncertainties concerning patient treatment (75.0%). A nuanced age-related variation emerged, with young healthcare workers (≤ 34 years old) experiencing stress at 90.80%, while older counterparts (> 35 years old) exhibited a higher proportion at 96.80%. Significant associations were found between years of work ($\chi^2 = 295.380, p = 0.000^*$) and age ($\chi^2 = 26.150, p = 0.000^*$) with work-related stress. Respondents with more than five years of work experience and those under the age of thirty-four reported higher levels of stress. Employment status also played a role, with full-time workers reporting varying stress levels compared to part-time and contractual workers ($\chi^2 = 8.279, p = 0.016^*$). No significant

associations were found for gender, marital status, or religion. The study further utilized multinomial regression analysis to explore predictors of work-related stress, revealing that individuals aged 35 and above, as well as those with more than 5 years of work experience, had higher odds of experiencing work-related stress in the high-level group.

Conclusion: This study provides a comprehensive understanding of work-related stress among healthcare professionals in Nigeria, highlighting its prevalence, sources, and determinants. By examining stress levels in various professions, identifying key predictors, and emphasizing the need to address specific stressors. This study lays the groundwork for future research and policy activities targeted at creating a workplace environment that encourages both professional success and personal well-being in the healthcare industry.

Keywords: Work related stress, Healthcare workers, Public hospitals, Service Delivery, Prevalence

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The work environment of the twentieth and twenty-first centuries is a rapidly expanding, dynamic, and highly exciting environment that offers its employees a plethora of advantages and chances. The stressful nature of such a workplace can exacerbate stress levels, particularly for individuals who often operate under pressure, such as bank employees, medical professionals, and others in the private sector. While pressure can be beneficial for improving performance, too much pressure can also result in stress, which has a depressing impact [1].

Irene [2] defines job stress as a series of reactions experienced by employees when they are presented with expectations for their work that do not align with their knowledge, skills, or capacities, and this interferes with their capacity to cope. This demonstrates how Irene's definition [2] links underemployment and a shortage of labor to job stress. According to Ajayi [1], another researcher also said that it is an inevitable part of modern life. Over the past century, there have been significant shifts in the nature of work, and these changes are currently occurring at lightning speed. It has had a detrimental impact on nearly every sector, from those in the medical and business fields to regular sales employees who experience stress at work. Workplace stress is frequently equated with unpleasant experiences, such as receiving a formal reprimand for subpar work from a manager or team leader. According to Islam [3], stress is often characterized as when individuals experience coercion in their daily lives. Workload-related stress is characterized by resistance to going to work and a persistent sense of pressure, along with other typical physiological, psychological, and behavioral stress indicators. Therefore, stress is defined as the negative physical

and psychological reactions that arise when an employee's needs, resources, or talents are not matched by the demands of their job. Employees have also stated that workplace stress might occasionally result in damage or bad health. Pahuja [4] defines stress as a zestful condition in which someone is faced with an opportunity, constraint, or demand related to what he or she wants and for which the result is perceived to be both uncertain and important. Stress results from a mismatch between the demands and pressures on the person, on the one hand, and their knowledge and abilities, on the other. Stress challenges the ability of many people to cope with work. This includes not only situations where the pressures of work exceed the worker's ability to cope but also situations where the worker's knowledge and abilities are not sufficiently utilized, and that is a problem for them. One of the most pressing problems facing the health care industry is stress, which must be addressed in order for workers to comfortably deliver high-quality work. Because stress may result in depression, which harms one's health, attitude, and job behavior, it creates an imbalance in one's life. Over time, the healthcare industry in Nigeria has been recognized as one of the most demanding. For example, at many hospitals, employees deal with patients who have diseases or injuries that might be fatal, and these situations can be made more difficult by the employees' busy schedules, the unbalanced staff-to-patient ratio, or even personal issues. Emergencies on the job further complicate an already stressful work situation. To further add to this, health care workers have to accommodate demanding patients, especially those suffering from chronic debilitating diseases as well as those experiencing acute or severe pains [5]. Despite what is happening, what is felt, and expressed needs that exert varying amounts of pressure and stress in the health care workplace, their work outputs, and service delivery, not much has been done to generate scientific evidence on how to effectively address the stress felt by health care practitioners within the health care delivery system in Nigeria [6]. According to research, workplace initiatives

that address stress avoidance promote pleasant working conditions for health workers, reducing stress and, as a result, improving or consolidating service delivery. According to Jennings [7], personnel in human service professions, such as the health industry, are frequently obliged to spend a significant amount of time in intense interaction with patients, and when patients are not responded to quickly, the situation can become unpleasant and highly demanding. Onigbogi's [8] empirical investigation of the presence of stress in the Nigerian health care industry sheds additional light on the presence of stress-causing elements in the Nigerian health care sector. The issue of work stress among Nigerian health care workers could be better addressed if the factors responsible for such stress were properly identified and evaluated. The effect of work stress among health care workers is a topic to be considered, and the question of how work stress affects health care workers' performance is a relevant one given the nature of today's health care environment and the challenges faced by Nigerian health care workers in their day-to-day affairs. The current work environment of health care workers is confronted with increasing complexities such as understaffing, workloads, lack of resources, distractions from patient relations, etc. This prompted the need for the study to explore the prevalence of work-related stress among health-related workers in the FCT, Abuja. According to World Health Organization (WHO) [35], occupational stress is defined as "harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, and needs of the worker. Stress is a response to stressors and can be positive or negative in nature. Different findings showed that individuals and organizations are largely affected by occupational stress. Despite this, it affects all employed professionals; the burden is too high among health care workers. Occupational stress is a major reason for work-related delays, absenteeism, hypertension, musculoskeletal disorders, cardiovascular disorders, and substance use. Moreover, it is also a major cause of mental

disturbance, injuries, and staff turnover. It also reduces organizational commitment, job satisfaction, quality of care, and productivity. Occupational stress is a second work-related problem next to low back pain.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

A slew of organizations, particularly in the health-care sector, are reporting an alarming increase in the harmful consequences of stress on staff productivity [9]. Organizations seeking increased productivity end up asking more from their staff, overloading them with work in order to meet deadlines, which can have a negative impact on their employees' psychological and physical well-being. This may have the opposite effect of what these groups intend [10]. The empirical link between stress and employee performance has not been addressed. Sharmilee [11] studies found a substantial negative link between occupational stress and employee performance in the health industry. According to Ajayi [1], pressures can cause stress, which is usually the consequence of a mix of stressful situations that compound over time. Some people grow so used to the signs of chronic stress that they go unrecognized, to their disadvantage. The majority of job stress is connected to work management, workplace relationships, organizational layout, and whether you feel you have authority and control over your work. Everybody experiences stress in a different way [1]. Since some people are more impacted than others, what stresses one person out might not worry another out. It may vary based on your personality type and the way you've been trained to handle pressure [12].

The Health Advocates Etim [6] states Sixty to eighty percent of workplace accidents and near-misses are thought to be caused by stress-related attention or tiredness. In 2008, the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) reported that stress reactions and job dissatisfaction account for 60% to 90% of health care workers' unsatisfactory attitudes toward

patients. Chronic underfunding, deteriorating medical facilities, a lack of staff, and inadequate equipment have all negatively impacted the Nigerian health system and caused stress for medical professionals. The majority of healthcare workers in Nigeria, particularly those in the secondary and basic care levels, operate in extremely difficult and unfavorable environments, which increases their stress levels at work [6]. Workplace stress reduces output in terms of both quality and quantity, and it has been linked to several incidents or near misses in the healthcare industry, which has an impact on service delivery [6]. A multitude of health issues are linked to occupational stress among workers. Stress at work has been connected to decreased productivity, a rise in occupational accidents, and low job satisfaction [13]. It's a common misconception that fatigued staff members are more likely to misuse equipment, endangering patients or staff members in the process.

1.3 Justification/Rationale of the study

Stress manifests itself physiologically, psychologically, behaviorally, and organizationally. All of these factors eventually have an impact on workplace performance, resulting in organizational impacts such as absenteeism, job turnover, a negative organizational atmosphere, and decreased productivity. Health care personnel must be free of occupational stress and in excellent health in order to satisfy the physical and emotional demands of their job.

1.4 Research Questions

The research questions that would be used for this study are stated below:

1. What is the effect of work stress on health care workers in Nigerian health care sector?
2. What are the causes of stress faced by healthcare workers in the Nigerian health care sector?
3. What are the strategies used for dealing with work stress among health care workers?

1.5 General and Specific objectives

1.5.1 General objectives

The general objective of this study will be to determine the prevalence, sources and determinants of work-related stress among health care workers in selected health care facilities in FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

1.5.2 Specific objectives

The specific objectives of this study will be to:

- i. To determine the prevalence of work-related stress.
- ii. To determine the sources of work related stress to health care workers in the study area.
- iii. To determine how work related stress affects service delivery in the health care sector.
- iv. To assess the determinants/predictors of work related stress among health care workers in the selected hospitals for this study.

Hypothesis of the research

In order to enable the researcher, ascertain the relationship between the variables involved in this research, he has to propose the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis One

Ho: work stress does not affect health care worker.

H_A: work stress does affect health care worker.

Hypothesis Two

Ho: work stress does not have a significant negative impact on the effectiveness of a Nigerian health care worker.

H_A: work stress does have a significant negative impact on the effectiveness of a Nigerian health care worker.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter intends to review the literature with respect to the study. Issues considered in this section would include work stress, facilitators of stress (work overload, role of conflict, and role of ambiguity), performance, and the impact of stress on performance.

2.2 Job Stress

According to Malek [14], job stress is an uncomfortable emotional predicament that an individual experiences when job needs are not matched with his ability to cope with the scenario. It is a well-known phenomenon that manifests differently in different work contexts and affects workers differently. Jamshed [15] proposed it. A person working in a bank may experience stress. "The workplace is potentially an important source of stress for bankers because of the amount of time they spend in their respective banks." Furthermore, stress frequently impairs their performance. "As a result, individuals' occupations may be a major source of stress in the given circumstances." Burnout occurs when individuals experience stress as a result of diverse occupational situations and fail to manage stress (IBDM). Basically, in the banking industry, a lack of administrative assistance from a supervisor (manager), work overload and time constraints, the riskiness of a job, bad relationships with clients and coworkers, and a work-family balance all contribute to stress, which reduces employee performance. The same was supplied by Mahmood [16]. "Causes of stress are many, like workload, cuts in staff, change at work, long work hours, shift work, lack of supervision, inadequate training, inappropriate working conditions, too heavy responsibilities, and poor relations with colleagues." Malek [14] stated that "a large and multi-field literature points to a lot of key factors such as work environment, management support, and workload in determining how stressful the work can be and its effect on employee physical and mental health."

Toshimichi [17] defines stress as "the interaction between an individual and the environment that produces emotional strain that affects a person's physical and mental condition." Stress is induced by stressors, which are events that disrupt an individual's homeostasis. These scholars also emphasized that excessive stress has a tremendous cost on individuals, companies, and society. Many employees may suffer from anxiety problems or diseases caused by stress. It is estimated that each afflicted employee misses around 16 working days per year due to stress, anxiety, or sadness.

2.3 Types of Stress

Taylor[18] stated that there are four major types of stress, which she explains as follows:

Acute stress: This type of stress is the most common and most recognizable form of stress. This is the kind of stress which the individual knows exactly why he is stressed. Normally, the body rests when these stressful events cease and life gets back to normal because the effects are short-term. Acute stress usually does not cause severe or permanent damage to the body.

Traumatic stress: It is a severe stress reaction that results from a catastrophic event or intense experience such a natural disaster, sexual assault, life-threatening accidents, or participation in combat. Here, after the initial shock and emotional fallout, many trauma victims gradually begin to recover. But for some people, the psychological and physical symptoms triggered by the trauma do not go away. The body does not return to equilibrium, and life does not return to normal.

This condition is known as post-trauma stress disorder. Common symptoms of this type of stress are flashbacks or nightmares about the trauma, avoidance of places and things associated with the trauma, hyper vigilance for signs of danger and irritability and tension. Chronic stress: She describes this type of stress as unrelenting demands and pressures seemingly interminable periods of time. This stress wears the individual down day after day and year after year with no visible

escape. It grinds away both emotional and health of the individual leading to breakdown and even death.

Episodic acute stress: This episodic acute stress is a situation where the individual's life experiencing this type of stress is very chaotic, out of control and they always seem to be facing multiple stressful situations. They are always in a rush, always late, always taking on too many projects, handling too many demands. Those who are prone to this type of stress include "TYPE A" personality. If an individual is prone to episodic acute stress, he may not know it or admit it. He may be wedded to a lifestyle that promotes stress. Unfortunately, people with episodic acute stress may find it so habitual that they resist changing their lifestyle until they experience a severe physical symptom. Impact of stress on employee productivity

2.4 Sources of Stress

Matthew[19] defined stress can be experienced from four basic sources.

The Environment– the environment can bombard you with intense and competing demands to adjust. Examples of environmental stressors include weather, noise, crowding, pollution, traffic, unsafe environment, and substandard housing, and crime.

Social Stressors– we can experience multiple stressors arising from the demands of the different social role we occupy, such as parent, spouse, caregiver, and employee. Some examples of social stressors include deadlines, financial problems, job interviews, presentations, disagreements, presentations, disagreements demand for your time and attention loss of a loved one, divorce and co-parenting.

Physiological– situation and circumstances affecting our body can be experienced as physiological stressors. Examples of physiological stressors include rapid growth of adolescence, menopause, illness, aging, giving birth, accidents, lack of exercise, poor nutrition, and sleep disturbances.

Thoughts— your brain interprets and perceives situations as stressful, difficult, painful, or pleasant. Some situations in life are stress provoking, but it is our thought that determines whether they are a problem.

2.5 Factors that Contribute to Work Stress

Work-overload

Rehman [20] Physical symptoms are linked to high levels of stresses such as a severe workload and confusion regarding the supervisor's expectations. When an employee fails to meet the demands of the work and the supervisor, stress results. Schnall, working circumstances include an excessive workload and contradictory expectations. 40% of workers said their job is highly stressful. In the United States, 80 percent of employees are stressed at work. Previous research by Bacharach[21] has identified many variables connected with occupational stress. Work overload, for example, occurs when an employee's job demands outnumber the resources or time available to accomplish given obligations. Manzoor states that a number of factors, including workload, peer attitude, salary, bonuses, and job schedule, can lead to stress among employees. The primary causes of stress among employees are workload, technology issues, greater goals, pay and remuneration, decision-making results, management and peer support behaviors, and longer work hours. According to Dar et al., stress rises with a higher title, and elements that contribute to stress in workers include a sense of undervaluation, the work-home interface, fear of losing one's job, traumatic work-related experiences, and unstable economic conditions. Khattak[22] stated that in Pakistan, employees experienced stress because of workload, technological problems at work, long working hours, inadequate salary, insufficient time for family and job worries at home. Stress is a cause of dissatisfaction among the employees like role conflicts, work intensification, relationship with Colleagues and unfavorable working conditions are the major factors of creating stress In health

sector, where female faces a stressful situation due to irregular and long working hours, role pressure and Work overload, they may become nervous and anxious.). Inflexible work hours, work overload, risky job and poor coworker relations are the main contributors to job stress, which create dissatisfaction among the employees.

Role of Conflict

Rosen[23] stated that role conflict refers to incompatible requirements and expectations that the employees receive from their supervisor or coworker. Nwadiani, whom an individual must interact hold conflicting expectations about that individual's behavior. There are three different major types of role conflict. One of them is the conflict between the person and the role. For example, a production worker and a member of a union are appointed to head up a new production team. This new team leader may not really believe in keeping close control over the workers and it would go against this individual's personality to be hardnosed but that is what the head of production would expect. The second type of interpersonal role conflict creates contradictory expectations about how a given role should be played. Finally, inter-role conflict results from differing requirements of two or more roles that must be played at the same time. For example, work roles and non-work roles are often in such conflict.

Zhao [24] stated that the role arises when more demands have been taken place upon the individual by the peers, supervisors, subordinates. Such type of stress is more dominant in the jobs which have lack of descriptions or unclear descriptions and these require conceptual thinking and decision making. f stress on employee productivity

Role Ambiguity

Malek[14] stated that the employees become ambivalent to predict their supervisor's reactions to their tasks as "success" or as "failure." Finally, long hours, work overload, time pressure, difficult

or complex tasks, lack of breaks, lack of variety and poor work conditions (for example, space, temperature, light) are causes of occupational stress.

Performance

Meneze[25] defined performance as the employee's ability to produce work or goods and services according to the expected standards set by the employers, or beyond the expected standards. Mathis et al. defined performance as a measure of the quantity and quality of work done considering the cost of the resource it took to do the work.

2.6 Effects of work Stress among health care workers

Khattak [26] stated that stress has drastic effects on employees. Employees in stress cannot meet the expectations of their organization because they are facing physical, psychological, and organizational burnout. Ismail & Hong [27] describe that employees in service organizations are subjected to a high degree of work-related stress, which is the major reason for employees' poor performance at work. Work stress affects the female employee's well-being negatively, which creates dissatisfaction and negative emotions towards work and ultimately decreases their performance. According to Tsaur [28], most of the employees in organizations feel that their work is stressful, which in turn decreases their performance. Barbara et al. define the condition of "high demand and low control" as highly associated with cardiovascular and heart problems, anxiety, demoralization, depression, use of drugs (alcohol), and susceptibility to a wide range of infectious diseases. The condition of "high effort and low control" is also associated with a high rate of cardiovascular, anxiety, depression, and conflict-related problems. Where both of these conditions are present, high incidents of back pain and receptive strain injuries occur. Collectively, both of these conditions stifle the performance of employees.

Malek[14] stated that employees having no control over their work, lack of financial rewards, unsupportive management system face serious physical problems, such as heart disease; increase in blood pressure and headaches. The author further mentioned that at job, stress affects the physical, psychological and financial balance of the employees. In a research paper on stress result show, employees are absent from organization and loose working hours based on stress. Shehzad[29] stated stress increases the employee turnover on the job, which influences the employees general performance as well as organizational performance.

According to Salami[30] stress directly affects the employees' performance and both are mutually related to each other, without stress, there is a death of human being. Coetzee and define role ambiguity, work relationships, job security, lack of job autonomy, work home interface, compensation and benefits, lack of management support are the key sources of creating job stress. Due to these sources of stress, employee engagement to work decreases. It negatively affects the performance of employees. It is estimated that 40 to 60 percent of all employees rate their jobs as being stress and having drastic impact on their family balance and health. More than 70 percent of U.S workers think that there is no healthy link between their family lives and work, and more than 50 percent women in U.S have chosen to stop out from professional careers after large investment in formal education and training.

According to Bytyqi[31], stress has considerable importance for the organizational concern, because it has a direct effect on the employee's health and their performance. Stress influences the people both in positive and negative way. At initial stage, it influences positively by motivating employees, but if it is consistent for long time, it influences the people in negative way through increasing frustration, anxiety and tardiness. In the organization, if stress is not ignored then it destroys the profitability of the organization gradually. At job female employees are affected more

than the male employees through stress. With increase in age, job stress also increases. Hyperstress is found to be responsible for physical and psycho-physiological disorders, which leads to poor performance of an employ.

Chase[32] stated that Work-related stresses may be responsible for organizational outcomes such as decline in performance, dissatisfaction, lack of motivation and commitment, and an increase in absenteeism and turnover. stated that performance is measured in terms of outputs per labor hour. However, this measurement does not ensure that the firm will make money (for example when extra output is not sold, but accumulated as inventory). To test whether performance has increased, the following questions should be asked ‘has the action taken increased output or has it decreased inventory?’ “Has the action taken decreased operational expense?” This would then lead to a new definition which is: performance is all the actions that bring a company closer to its goals.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Area

This study will be conducted in AMAC Local Government Area, of the FCT, Nigeria. Three general hospitals are chosen Wuse, Maitama and Garki. The three hospitals have a land mass of 150 square kilometer.

3.2 Study Design

This will be descriptive cross-sectional study; the study will be made up of two components (quantitative and qualitative). The study will combine a qualitative and quantitative approach in its data collection. This method is deemed appropriate and useful because the present study involves direct and personal contact with health care workers [33]. The investigation took the form of a case study. A cross-sectional study is useful, especially when a holistic, in-depth investigation is required [33]. The researcher will use this method because it is more beneficial and enables her and the participants to discuss and describe their opinions in depth, with openness, and in detail. The researcher will employ a qualitative research design because she wants to focus on people's lives, behaviors, and organizational functioning. Furthermore, it is used by researchers who are interested in understanding the reason behind people's behavior or actions (Kerlinger, 33), which is the focus of this study. That is, to understand the reason behind the challenges of stress in the healthcare environment.

On the other hand, quantitative method deals in numbers, logic and objective stance Weiersman[34]. Using quantitative method gives more credibility to research as the study can usually be repeated or replicated due to its high reliability while using statistical numbers to explain what is observed (ibid). It is more efficient in generalizing research findings than the qualitative

particularly when data is based on random sampling Weiersman[34]. It is also relatively quick using the quantitative method to collect data (ibid) and works well when data samples are large (Punch, 2009). Data analysis using this method is relatively less time consuming than the qualitative Weiersman[34].

3.3 Study Population

The study populations will be health staff in the selected public hospitals in Wuse, Maitama and Garki FCT, Nigeria. There are (3) public hospitals selected for this study. The categories of health care workers that I am working with are nurses, medical doctors, laboratory scientist and pharmacist.

3.3.1 Inclusion Criteria

- 1) Nurses, doctors, laboratory scientist and pharmacist working in the 3 aforementioned general hospitals.
- 2) Nurses, doctors, laboratory scientist and pharmacist willing to participate through informed consent by answering yes or no for questions that will be included in the survey.

3.3.2 Exclusion Criteria

- 1) Respondents that are not Nurses, doctors, laboratory scientist and pharmacist will not be included in the aforementioned three general hospitals.
- 2) Respondents that are not willing to participate will not be included for the study.

3.4 Sample size determinant.

The Bluman's formula (2004) will be as used.

$$n = \frac{Z^2 p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

$$d^2$$

Where; **n** = the sample size

Z = Z-score (1.96) statistic corresponding to the level of prevalence

d = margin of error (7% = 0.07) precision

p = prevalence (50% = 0.5) expected prevalence

CI= 95% confidence interval

$$\mathbf{n = \underline{1.96^2 \times 0.5 (1 - 0.5)} = 196}$$

$$\mathbf{0.07^2}$$

$$\text{With 5\% non-response} = \underline{\mathbf{196 \times 5}} = \mathbf{9.8 + 196 = 206}$$

100

Since the total numbers of health care workers in the hospitals are unknown, then the calculated number in the sample size determinant is therefore to be used in the study. 206 questionnaires will be administered those who did not respond will be factored out.

3.4 Qualitative component:

This will consist of key informant interview (KII).

The instrument that will be used to collect data from respondents will be open-ended interviews that is, a face-to-face interview with key staff members of the hospitals with the utilization of an audio recorder and semi-structured interview guide that will be placed in the Appendix. The research question will be chosen based on 1) the topic 2) brainstorming on ideas 3) reading on general background information

3.5 Sampling Techniques.

A total of **206** respondents (health care workers) will be drawn from the three facilities.

Stage-I: Selection of Hospitals.

Wuse General Hospital, Maitama General Hospital and Garki General Hospital respectively will be selected using simple random sampling method

Stage-II: Selection of Departments.

Departments were selected in the hospitals and studied in no special order ranging from medical department, Laboratory department and nursing department.

Stage-III: Selection of Healthcare Workers.

A total of 206 respondents were chosen, with 68 healthcare professionals from each of the three institutions. The principal, 17 nurses, 17 doctors, 17 laboratory scientists, and 17 pharmacists will make up the study's sample. The approach of systematic random sampling was applied. This sampling methodology, according to Black [35], is a kind of probability sampling method in which sample members are chosen at random from a wider population based on a predetermined interval between sampling points. The entire population size is divided by the intended sample size to determine this interval, also known as the sampling interval. The names of the health workers on the nominal roll were used and every 2nd health worker in the list was selected until the 17 health workers required from the hospital were selected. Additionally, 2 health care workers would be interviewed from each group by the researcher. This will be a total of 68 respondents from each hospital.

3.6 Study Instruments.

The instruments for data collection will be self-administered questionnaire, key informant interviews; direct field observations. The questionnaires will have the following sections: Section A –Socio-demographic characteristics of health care workers this is for the researcher to know the participants of the research, Section B – Prevalence and Sources of Work-Related Stress, and Section C– Impact of work-related stress on service delivery in the healthcare sector.

3.7 Data collection method

The data collecting approach will begin with the delivery of a well-structured questionnaire to the individuals who have been chosen. The platform for this survey will be Google Forms, which will provide for an efficient and orderly data collection procedure. The questionnaire, which was meticulously designed to collect vital information on work-related stress among healthcare staff, will be distributed electronically to enhance accessibility and expedite responses.

The open-ended interview questions will be presented to the heads of each department sampled with the assistance of an assistant who will aid in the interview process. Only correctly completed instruments, however, will be evaluated.

3.8 Statistical Analysis

Data analysis will be carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) package version 25. Results will be presented in frequencies, percentages, and tables as appropriate. The results (data) obtained from this research is grouped according to specific objectives of the study. Bivariate analysis using chi-square as well as odds ratios (ORS), confidence intervals, and p-values will be done to determine the associations. Variables with a p-value of less than 0.2 in the bivariate analysis will be entered into the multinomial regression model for the final analysis. The significance level for the multinomial analysis will be set at $p < 0.05$.

3.9 Ethical considerations

The ethical approval for this study will be obtained from the ethics and research committee of the Federal Capital Territory. Corporation of heads of the health facilities will sort and respondents will be assured of the confidentiality of data.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS, ANALYSIS, AND EVALUATION OF FINDINGS

A total of 206 questionnaires were administered to respondents using google form questionnaire. 204 questionnaires were retrieved and valid for use after data cleaning. Two surveys were improperly filed. Thus, only 204 surveys were analyzed, giving a response rate of 99.0%.

Data analysis was conducted using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 27, with a significance level set at $P < 0.05$. To present categorical variables, frequencies and percentages were employed, while mean and standard deviation summarized quantitative variables. The Chi-square test elucidated factors linked to diverse stress domains, and multivariate analysis unveiled predictors of stress.

Table 4.1 Socio Demographic Characteristics of the respondents

Variables	Frequency (n=204)	Percentage %
Gender		
Male	111	54.41
Female	93	45.59
Age		
≤ 34	173	84.80
> 35	31	15.20
Mean age (years)	31.54±3.61	
Marital Status		
Single	66	32.4
Married	136	66.7
Widowed	1	0.5
Divorced/Separated	1	0.5
Profession		
Nurse	51	25.0
Doctor	51	25.0
Laboratory Scientist	51	25.0

Pharmacist	51	25.0
Educational Level		
PhD	13	6.37
Master	56	27.45
Bachelors	117	57.35
Diploma	18	8.82
Department		
Emergency	37	18.14
Laboratory	24	11.76
Medical wards	44	21.57
OPD	33	16.18
Others (Radiology, Obstetrics and gynecology)	10	4.90
Pediatrics wards	39	19.12
Surgical ward	17	8.33
Employment Status		
Full-time	178	87.3
Part-time	9	4.4
Contractual	17	8.3
Years of work experience		
≤ 5 years	70	65.69
≥ 6 years	134	34.31
Mean years of work	6.0±1.4	
Religion		
Christian	178	87.3
Muslim	26	12.7

Data Source: Field Survey (2023)

The study includes 204 healthcare workers with a gender distribution of 54.41% male and 45.59% female. The majority (84.80%) are aged 34 or below, with an average age of 31.54±3.61 years. Marital status shows 66.7% married individuals. Professions are evenly distributed, with 25% each for nurses, doctors, laboratory scientists, and pharmacists. Educational backgrounds vary, with the majority holding a Bachelor's degree (57.35%). The departmental distribution includes Emergency (18.14%), Laboratory (11.76%), and Medical Wards (21.57%). Employment is mostly full-time

(87.3%), and the majority have ≤ 5 years of work experience (65.69%). The religious affiliation is predominantly Christian (87.3%).

Table 4.2 Response rate on components of role and demand stress among health workers

Variables	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)	Total
Role						
Uncertainties on job duties and responsibilities increase work-related stress among health workers	0(0.0)	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	60(29.4)	136(66.7)	204
Not clear about what is expected of you at work can contribute to work related-stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	9(4.4)	77(37.7)	110(53.9)	204
Not having a clue on how to get your job done increase work-related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	8(3.9)	86(42.2)	102(50.0)	204
Not been clear on the goals and objectives of your department increase work-related stress.	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	112(54.9)	92(45.1)	204
Lack of understanding on how your job role fit into the overall aim of the organization increase work related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	9(4.4)	95(46.6)	92(45.1)	204
Demand						
High demands from different work department contribute to the prevalence of work-related stress.	8(3.9)	17(8.3)	0(0.0)	43(21.1)	136(66.7)	204
Tight deadlines contribute to work-related stress among health care workers.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	17(8.3)	51(25.0)	128(62.7)	204
Long working hours contribute to work-related stress among health care workers.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	43(21.1)	153(75.0)	204
Neglect of some task due to high work demand increase work-related stress among health care workers.	8(3.9)	8(3.9)	9(4.4)	59(28.9)	120(58.8)	204
Unrealistic time pressure increases work-related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	25(12.3)	70(34.3)	101(49.5)	204

Data Source: Field Survey (2023)

In the "Role" section, 136 respondents (66.7%) strongly agree that uncertainties in job duties and responsibilities increase work-related stress. In the "Demand" section, 136 (66.7%) respondents

strongly agree that high demands from different work departments contribute to work-related stress. The table effectively captures the varied perspectives of healthcare workers on the components of these stress-related factors.

Table 4.3 Response rate on components of relationship and support stress among health workers

Variables	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)	Total
Relationship						
Work place bullying can contribute to the prevalence of work-related stress among health care workers.	7(3.4)	0(0.0)	9(4.4)	61(29.9)	127(62.3)	204
Workplace harassment in form of unkind words or behavior contribute to work-related stress?	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	8(3.9)	61(29.9)	127(62.3)	204
Negative working relationships with both colleagues and superiors increase work- related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	68(33.3)	128(62.7)	204
Strained relationships at work increase work related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	9(4.4)	111(54.4)	76(37.3)	204
Instances of poor communication breakdown negatively affect work relationships.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	9(4.4)	52(25.5)	135(66.2)	204
Support						
Lack of support through emotionally demanding work can contribute to work-related stress among health care workers.	17(8.3)	0(0.0)	7(8.3)	51(25.0)	119(58.3)	204
Lack of support from colleagues and your supervisor can increase work-related stress among health care workers.	17(8.3)	0(0.0)	25(12.3)	93(45.6)	69(33.8)	204
Lack of supportive feedback on work done increase work related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	18(8.8)	87(42.6)	91(44.6)	204
Lack of employee support programs by the organization tend to increase work related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	18(8.8)	60(29.4)	118(57.8)	204

Lack of assistance from colleagues when the work gets difficult increase work related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	18(8.8)	76(37.3)	102(50.0)	204
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Data Source: Field Survey (2023)

In the "Relationship" section, 128 respondents (62.7%) strongly agree that strained relationships at work increase work-related stress, while in the "Support" section, 119 participants (58.3%) strongly agree that lack of support through emotionally demanding work can contribute to work-related stress. The table highlights the most prevalent perspectives on the impact of relationship and support factors on work-related stress among healthcare workers.

Table 4.4 Response rate on components of change and control stress among health workers

Variables	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)	Total
Change						
Insufficient opportunities to question supervisors about change at work can contribute to work-related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	111(54.4)	85(41.7)	204
Frequent policy and procedure changes tend to increase work related stress.	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	35(17.2)	103(50.5)	66(32.4)	204
Coping with the pace of changes in the healthcare sector can be challenging.	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	25(12.3)	112(54.9)	67(32.8)	204
Lack of effective training by the organization when introducing changes increase work-related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	8(3.9)	77(37.7)	111(54.4)	204
When changes are made at work, uncertainties on how they will work out in practice increase work related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	9(4.4)	121(59.3)	66(32.4)	204
Control						
Inflexible work time increase the incidence of work-related stress.	8(3.9)	9(4.4)	9(4.4)	60(29.4)	118(57.8)	204
Not having a choice in deciding your work speed increase work-	8(3.9)	8(3.9)	18(8.8)	76(37.3)	94(46.1)	204

related stress among health care workers.						
Not having a say on when to go on break increase work related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	17(8.3)	129(63.2)	50(24.5)	204
Not having a choice in how your work is done increase work related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	146(71.6)	50(24.5)	204
Not having a say to some extent over the way you work, increase work related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	8(3.9)	95(46.6)	93(45.6)	204

Data Source: Field Survey (2023)

In the "Change" section, 121 respondents (59.3%) agree that uncertainties about how changes at work will work out in practice increase work-related stress. In the "Control" section, 146 participants (71.6%) strongly agree that not having a choice in how their work is done increases work-related stress. The table provides insights into the impact of change and control factors on work-related stress among healthcare workers, with a focus on the most frequently expressed perspectives.

Table 4.5 Prevalence of work related stress among health care workers

Domains	High n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Low n(%)
Role	136 (66.7%)	60 (29.4%)	8 (3.9%)
Demand	136 (66.7%)	51 (25.0%)	17 (8.3%)
Relationship	128 (62.7%)	68 (33.3%)	8 (3.9%)
Support	119 (58.3%)	93 (45.6%)	8 (3.9%)
Change	111 (54.4%)	103 (50.5%)	9 (4.4%)
Control	118 (57.8%)	60 (29.4%)	17 (8.3%)

Data Source: Field Survey (2023)

Work-related stress is prevalent among healthcare workers, manifesting across different domains. In the "Role" category, 66.7% experience high stress, while 29.4% are neutral, and 3.9% report low stress. Similarly, in the "Demand" domain, 66.7% face high stress, with 25.0% being neutral and 8.3% indicating low stress. The "Relationship" domain sees 62.7% experiencing high stress, 33.3% being neutral, and 3.9% reporting low stress. Concerning "Support," 58.3% encounter high

stress, 45.6% are neutral, and 3.9% indicate low stress. In the "Change" domain, 54.4% report high stress, 50.5% are neutral, and 4.4% indicate low stress. Lastly, in the "Control" domain, 57.8% experience high stress, 29.4% are neutral, and 8.3% report low stress. These findings underscore the widespread impact of work-related stress across various dimensions of healthcare work.

Table 4.6 Sources of work related stress among health care workers

Variables	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)	Total
Interpersonal conflict among physicians and other health care workers can contribute to work-related stress.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	18(8.8)	42(20.6)	136(66.7)	204
Traumatic events, such as work place death contributes to work-related stress	0(0.0)	8(3.9)	17(8.3)	70(34.3)	109(53.4)	204
Heavy workloads contribute to work-related stress among health care workers.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	52(25.5)	144(70.6)	204
Uncooperative patients and their families can increase work related stress	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	17(8.3)	76(37.3)	103(50.5)	204
Uncertainties concerning patient treatment increase work related stress.	8(3.9)	8(3.9)	35(17.2)	86(42.2)	67(32.8)	204

Data Source: Field Survey (2023)

The majority (66.7%) agreed that interpersonal conflict among colleagues is a major source of stress among healthcare workers. Whereas traumatic incidents, severe workloads, recalcitrant patients or families, and uncertainty concerning patient treatment were identified as stresses by 53.4%, 70.6%, 50.5%, and 32.8%, respectively. These findings offer light on the many elements that influence work-related stress in the healthcare profession.

Table 4.7 Impact of work-related stress on service delivery among respondents

Variables	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)	Total
Work-related stress affects the quality of service delivery in the healthcare sector.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	9(4.4)	18(8.8)	169(82.8)	204
Work-related stress among healthcare workers has led to decreased attentiveness or concentration in service delivery.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	18(8.8)	9(4.4)	169(82.8)	204
Work-related stress contributes to reduced productivity in service delivery.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	9(4.4)	26(12.7)	161(78.9)	204
Work-related stress increases the likelihood of medical errors or mistakes in service delivery.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	18(8.8)	26(12.7)	152(74.5)	204
Work related stress has an adverse impact on patient satisfaction with the healthcare services provided.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	44(21.6)	152(74.5)	204

Data Source: Field Survey (2023)

The findings unveils that majority (82.8%) strongly agree that work-related stress affects the quality of service delivery in the healthcare sector. Similarly, 82.8% strongly agree that work-related stress among healthcare workers leads to decreased attentiveness or concentration in service delivery. Reduced productivity in service delivery is acknowledged by 78.9% of respondents. Additionally, 74.5% strongly agree that work-related stress increases the likelihood of medical errors or mistakes in service delivery. The adverse impact of work-related stress on patient satisfaction is recognized by 74.5%.

Table 4.8 Impact of work-related stress on service delivery among respondents

Variables	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)	Total
Delays in service delivery can occur as a result of work-related stress among healthcare workers.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	45(22.1)	151(74.0)	204
Work-related stress contributes to increased absenteeism, affecting service delivery.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	45(22.1)	151(74.0)	204
Work-related stress hampers effective teamwork among healthcare	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	45(22.1)	151(74.0)	204

professionals, impacting coordinated service delivery.						
Work-related stress may result in reduced patient trust and satisfaction with healthcare services.	8(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	62(30.4)	134(65.7)	204
Work-related stress increases the likelihood of healthcare professionals seeking alternative employment.	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	8(3.9)	36(17.6)	160(78.4)	204
Implementation of enhanced support programs and resources can help alleviate work-related stress.	16(7.8)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	18(8.8)	170(83.3)	204

Data Source: Field Survey (2023)

The findings reveal that 74% strongly agree that delays in service delivery can occur due to work-related stress, an equal percentage strongly agrees that work-related stress contributes to increased absenteeism, affecting service delivery. Moreover, 74% strongly agree that work-related stress hampers effective teamwork among healthcare professionals, impacting coordinated service delivery. A substantial 65.7% strongly agree that work-related stress may result in reduced patient trust and satisfaction with healthcare services. Additionally, 78.4% strongly agree that work-related stress increases the likelihood of healthcare professionals seeking alternative employment. On a positive note, 83.3% believe that the implementation of enhanced support programs and resources can help alleviate work-related stress.

Table 4.9 Factors associated with work-related stress among respondents

Variable	High level n(%)	Neutral n(%)	Low level n(%)	Chi Square (χ^2)	P value
Gender					
Male	104	1	6	0.328	0.849
Female	187	9	8		
Years of Work					
≤ 5	65	3	2	295.380	0.000*
≥ 6	122	6	6		
Age					
≤ 34	157	8	8	26.150 F	0.000*
> 35	30	1	0		
Marital Status					

Single	58	0	8		
Married	127	9	0	1.654	0.437
Widowed	1	0	0		
Divorced / Separated	1	0	0		
Employment Status					
Full-time	178	0	0	8.279	0.016*
Part-time	0	9	0		
Contractual	8	0	9		
Religion					
Christian	161	9	8	2.709	0.258
Islam	26	0	0		

* = statistically significant F = Fisher's Exact Test

The chi-square test outcomes reveal noteworthy connections between Work-Related Stress (WRS) linked to service delivery and certain demographic factors. Notably, there is a significant association between years of work ($\chi^2 = 295.380$, $p = 0.000^*$) and age ($F = 26.150$, $p = 0.000^*$) with the attribute levels. Employment status also shows significance ($\chi^2 = 8.279$, $p = 0.016^*$). Gender, marital status, and religion, on the other hand, do not demonstrate statistically significant associations with the attribute levels based on the provided Chi Square (χ^2) and P values

Table 4.10 Multinomial regression analysis for the predictors of work-related stress due to service delivery among respondents

Predictor Variable	P-value	AOR	95% CI for OR	
			Lower	Upper
High level				
Age				
≤ 34	0.017*	0.312	0.120	0.811
> 35		1		
Years of work experience				
≤ 5	0.44*	0.274	0.076	0.986
≥ 6		1		
Low level				
Age				

≤ 34	< 0.001*	3.859E+7	3.859E+7	3.859E+7
> 35		1		
Years of work experience				
≤ 5	0.324	0.439	0.086	2.256
≥ 6		1		

* = statistically significant

The group with a low level of agreement suggests that age significantly influences the likelihood of agreeing that work-related stress affects the quality of service delivery, as indicated by the very low p-value (<0.001). However, years of work experience do not show a significant association (p = 0.609) in this group. In the high-level agreement group, age and years of work experience demonstrates statistically significant impacts on the odds of agreement, with p-values of 0.017 and 0.44, respectively. These findings suggest that both age and years of work experience play a role in shaping perceptions of the impact of work-related stress on service delivery.

QUALITATIVE PART

Table 4.11: Information on participants

Code given to participant	gender	Age	Position of staff In hospital	Research site
A1	M	47	Consultant doctor	Hospital A
A2	F	42	Chief Nursing officer	Hospital B
A3	M	39	HOD Medical laboratory science	Hospital C
A4	F	40	HOD Pharmacy	Hospital D

Data Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 4.12 Interview schedule

Participant	Date of interview	Time	Position of staff in the Hospital	Department
A1	19/03/2023	04mins45secs	Consultant doctor	Pediatrics
A2	21/03/2023	03mins51secs	Chief Nursing officer	Nursing

A3	22/03/2023	04mins48secs	HOD Medical laboratory science	laboratory
A4	27/03/2023	03mins30secs	HOD Pharmacy	pharmacy

Data Source: Field Survey (2023)

4.1 THEMES EMANATING FROM THE EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION

Theme 1: Effects of Work Stress on Health Care Workers:

Sub-theme: Impact of stress on Professional Performance

In dissecting the effects of work stress, Participant A1, the Consultant Doctor from Hospital A, unveiled how stress permeates decision-making and job performance. Stress, he highlighted, can compromise the precision and efficacy of clinical judgments, laying bare the vulnerability of healthcare workers under its influence.

Sub-theme: Emotional Toll on Patient Care

A2, the Chief Nursing officer from Hospital B, painted a vivid picture of stress's toll on patient care. She remarked, *"Stress has a direct impact on the quality of care we provide, affecting not only patient outcomes but also our own emotional well-being."*

Sub-theme: Precision Challenges in Laboratory Work and Medication Dispensation

From Hospital C, A3, the HOD Medical laboratory science, and A4, the HOD Pharmacy from Hospital D, echoed the sentiment that stress extends its tendrils into the precision of their respective domains. A3 detailed how stress compromises precision in laboratory processes, while A4 emphasized the impact on accurate medication dispensation, highlighting the interconnectedness of stress and the potential risks it poses.

Theme 2: Causes of Stress Faced by Healthcare Workers:

Sub-theme: Workload and Staffing Challenges

The participants unanimously highlighted the burden of high workload and insufficient staffing levels across the healthcare sector. The strain of managing heavy patient loads emerged as a common thread, underscoring the pivotal role of staffing in alleviating stress.

Sub-theme: Bureaucratic Obstacles and Resource Constraints

The collective voice of participants from Hospitals A-D pointed to bureaucratic hurdles and inadequate resources as significant stressors. Administrative complexities, coupled with a lack of essential equipment and infrastructure, created a challenging environment that heightened stress levels.

Sub-theme: Interprofessional Conflicts and Performance Targets

Interprofessional conflicts and the pressure to meet performance targets emerged as additional stress-inducing factors. The complexities of workplace dynamics and the challenges associated with achieving organizational goals weighed heavily on the participants, fostering a stressful environment.

Theme 3: Strategies for Dealing with Work Stress:

Sub-theme: Social Support and Teamwork

The qualitative narratives illuminated the importance of social support and teamwork as essential coping mechanisms. A1 and A3 shared experiences of seeking support within their teams, emphasizing the significance of a collaborative and supportive work environment.

Sub-theme: Mindfulness Practices and Professional Development

Engagement in mindfulness practices and participation in professional development programs emerged as strategies employed to navigate work-related stress. A2 and A4 discussed the role of continuous learning and personal growth in fostering resilience and coping with stress.

Sub-theme: Work-Life Balance and Organizational Support

A4, the HOD Pharmacy, underscored the importance of maintaining a healthy work-life balance. Participants collectively highlighted the need for organizational support, including well-defined policies and interventions to address work-related stress systematically.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

Negative physical and emotional responses resulting from a mismatch between job requirements and an employee's capabilities, resources, or needs are collectively referred to as work-related stress (WRS). Nosocomial stress, a term used to describe stressors in hospital settings, includes things like an excessive workload, understaffing, out-of-date equipment, little opportunities for career advancement, subpar management, relationships between coworkers, poor working conditions, long work hours, etc. [36]. This ascertained the frequency and determinants of stress at work among medical practitioners.

The workforce in healthcare is shown in the demographic overview as a largely youthful, diversified population with a range of educational backgrounds and degrees of experience. The distinct makeup of healthcare professionals in FCT Abuja is depicted by a number of factors, including age, gender distribution, marital status, occupation, and religious affiliation. Comprehending these demographics is essential to customizing treatments to target the unique requirements of individuals in an ever-evolving workforce.

Work-related stress was shown to be widespread among healthcare professionals across several domains, including role, demand, connection, support, change, and control. Within the Role and demand domain, a higher percentage of respondents indicated a high degree of WRS. As indicated by a substantial number of respondents, this might be due to uncertainty in work assignments, responsibilities, and excessive requests from different departments. Job tasks, responsibilities, and unreasonable demands have been identified as major stressors that can lead to physical and mental health issues, resulting in poor service delivery among healthcare workers, and lowering the likelihood of achieving specific goals and objectives within the health sector. The finding is

consistent with research conducted in Calabar, Nigeria, which revealed that stresses such as overtime and workload impair healthcare personnel's wellbeing and productivity [37]. Also, a study by Kikuchi et al. [38] explored the connection between the duration of overtime work and stress responses among Japanese workers, confirming a correlation between the two. Wong, Chan, and Ngan's [39] investigation into the impact of extended working hours on occupational health revealed a meta-analysis demonstrating a correlation between long working hours and adverse occupational health effects. Additionally, Taris et al. [40] found in their study that overtime work correlates with adverse subjective health, although not with body mass."

The poor relationship in this study was found to cause a high level of stress among the participants. The reason might be due to negative working relationships with both colleagues and superiors, harassment and bullying as reported by most of the participants. Studies have identified workplace bullying as a major stressor affecting a significant proportion of healthcare professionals [41]. Quine [42] discovered in a study of nurses in the United Kingdom that those who had experienced one or more forms of bullying were more likely to criticize aspects of the organizational climate. These criticisms included increased workload, increased role ambiguity, decreased participation in decision-making, and decreased control over work. This finding is consistent with the idea that perceptions of the workplace can be influenced by a variety of factors, including negative affectivity and other individual variables [43].

The findings from this study also highlighted key sources of work-related stress (WRS) among healthcare workers. These sources can contribute to significant emotional distress and stress among healthcare workers [44]. The impact of work-related stress on service delivery in the healthcare sector is evident from the survey results. This includes a negative impact on the quality of service, decreased attentiveness, reduced productivity, and an increased likelihood of medical

errors. Moreover, work-related stress is associated with delays in service delivery, heightened absenteeism, impaired teamwork among healthcare professionals, reduced patient trust and satisfaction, and an increased likelihood of healthcare professionals seeking alternative employment.

The multinomial regression analysis identifies age and years of work experience as significant predictors of stress among healthcare professionals. Similar to a study in western Ghana, this indicates that older employees are less prone to stress than their younger counterparts. The association between age, marital status, workload, educational background, and stress levels underscores the vulnerability of younger, less-experienced healthcare professionals to work-related stress, potentially compromising service quality [45]. This is also consistent with a recent study by Alkatheri et al. [46] and Lambert [47], but it differs from Salam [48] and Sveinsdottir et al. [49]. These findings highlight the complicated link between age, years of work experience, and the likelihood of experiencing work-related stress in different agreement groups, emphasizing the importance of considering these factors in the context of service delivery in the healthcare sector.

The qualitative component of this study unveils a rich tapestry of experiences, illuminating the multifaceted nature of work-related stress among healthcare workers in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The narratives provided by participants not only contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges faced but also underscore the resilience and coping mechanisms employed within the healthcare sector. The findings call for targeted interventions and systemic changes to foster a supportive and stress-resilient healthcare environment in Nigeria.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 Conclusion

Findings from this study has shown that the prevalence of stress among health care workers in the Federal capital territory, Abuja Nigeria is high. Having less than 5 years' work experience and being in the younger age group (<35 years) were noted as predictors of stress. Work related stress is a prevalent challenge and of significant public health importance particularly in the health care sector as seen from this study. These findings may influence development and implementation of occupational health policies which address psychosocial work hazard such as stress and also used as a baseline for implementation of interventions addressing work-related stress. There is a need for further research to explore more challenges pertaining to work related stress.

6.2 Recommendation

1. The National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA) and Federal Ministry of health should ensure more staff are employed across all departments in the various health care facilities in the FCT to reduce work related stress.
2. NPHCDA should provide Organizational Support by instituting support mechanisms, offering mental and physical health support, recognizing commendable work, and generally fostering a culture of appreciation for all primary health care workers.
3. FCT primary health care board should provide training and educational initiatives for healthcare personnel that attempt to improve their coping strategies, stress management abilities, and resilience.
4. The Federal Ministry of Health and NPHCDA should Institute mechanisms for continuous monitoring of stress levels among health care workers and their impact on service delivery effectiveness Monitoring absenteeism is one way to track employee stress, other available

tools include paying close attention to retention issues, the exit interviews conducted, annual employee satisfaction survey, the number of employees complains and unusual dips in productivity.

5. Healthcare workers can monitor stress through self-awareness of physical symptoms, emotional changes, disrupted sleep, decreased productivity, and strained social interactions.
6. Healthcare workers can manage workplace stress by practicing Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) Techniques which has been proven over time to tame the dangers of chronic stress. Therefore, establishing clear work-life balance and boundaries can be a lifesaver in preventing stress and burnout.

Addressing work-related stress is not only crucial for the well-being of healthcare professionals but also essential for enhancing the overall effectiveness of healthcare service delivery in Nigeria. The outlined recommendations serve as a guiding framework for organizations to establish a supportive and resilient environment, ensuring that healthcare practitioners can deliver optimal care to the communities they serve.

6.3 Contribution to knowledge:

1. The research determined the prevalence of work-related stress among health care workers to be high in the study area.
2. The research identified key predictors and determinants of work-related stress, thereby providing a better understanding of the factors that contribute to work-related stress among healthcare professionals in the study area
3. The research identified the sources of work-related stress, thereby giving a comprehensive insight into the stressors responsible for work related stress in the study area.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1 - Informed Consent Form

Informed Consent Form

Title of Study: Prevalence of Work-Related Stress and Its Determinants Among Health Care Workers in Selected Health Care Facilities in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Research Investigator Information

Name: Juliet Osalumese Orunwebho

Department of Public Health

Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria,

Kaduna State.

Phone No: 08115078183

E-mail: julietanthony42@gmail.com

Purpose of Study

You are being selected to participate in a research study and it is important to understand the purpose of the study. Please ask the researcher if there is anything unclear to you or in case you need more information about the study. The purpose of this study is to determine the prevalence of work-related stress and its determinant among health care workers.

Study Procedure

This study will be conducted on doctors, nurses, pharmacists and laboratory scientist and the information that is required from you would be stated in a questionnaire that you will fill. The information needed are your socio-demographic information, prevalence and sources of work related stress, and impact of work related stress on service delivery in the healthcare sector. The filling of the questionnaire would take an average of 8-10 minutes.

Risk and Benefits

There are no risks associated with this study because the information will be provided by you and no experiment would be conducted on you. However, if you are not interested in filling the questionnaire, you can withdraw from the study. Also, there are no direct benefits for your participation in this study, however, we hope that the information obtained from you in this study will be used to increase knowledge on prevalence of work-related stress and its determinants among health care workers.

Confidentiality

Your information will be kept anonymous and confidential. Your name isn't needed for the study; hence codes will be generated for each participant to identify your response on the questionnaires in to order to avoid mix up. The collected data would be stored in a password protected file.

Contact information

If there are any questions about this study, you can contact the researcher whose information is provided above and if you have any question about your right as a research participant, you can contact the ethical review committee, Health and Human Services Secretariat, FCTA, Abuja.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation for this study is voluntary and not compulsory, hence you are not under any obligation to partake in the study. If you decide to take part in the study, you will be asked to sign a consent form showing your interest in the study. Please note that you can withdraw from this study at any time before the completion of the data collection.

Consent

I have read and understand the provided information and had the opportunity to ask questions about the study. I understand that my participation isn't compulsory, and I can withdraw at any time without any implication, hence I voluntarily agree to take part in this study and provide my correct information on the questionnaire.

Participant's Signature..... Date

Investigator's Signature Date

Appendix 2 - Questionnaire

My name is Juliet.O. Orunwebho, I am a postgraduate student at the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria conducting a research on: Prevalence of Work-Related Stress and its Determinants among Health Care Workers in Selected Health Care Facilities in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja - Nigeria.

You have been selected by chance to be part of this study. I wish to respectfully request for your permission to administer this questionnaire to you. All information obtained in the course of this interview will be kept confidential and will only be used for the purpose of this research and your participation is voluntary. You have the right to refuse participation or withdraw from the study. Thank you.

Section A –Socio-demographic characteristics of health care workers

Questions	Responses	
1. Gender	Male	1
	Female	2
2. Age	≤ (Less than or equal to) 34	1
	>(Greater than) 35	2
3. What is your marital status?	Single	1
	Married	2
	Divorced/Separated	3
	Widowed	4
4. What is your designation?	Doctor	1
	Nurse	2
	Laboratory scientist	3
	Pharmacist	4
	Others	5
5. Respondent highest qualification attained?	PhD	1
	Masters	2
	Bachelors	3
	Diploma	4
6. Which department are you working in?	Emergency	1
	Laboratory	2
	Medical wards	3
	OPD	4
	Pediatrics wards	5

	Surgical ward	6
	Others	7
7. Employment Status	Full-time	1
	Part-time	2
	Contractual	3
8. Years of work experience	≤ (Less than or equal to) 5 years	1
	≥ (Greater than or equal to) 6 years	2
9. Religion	Christianity	1
	Islam	2
	Others	3

Section B: Prevalence and Sources of Work-Related Stress.

Item	Response				
	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)
10. Uncertainties on job duties and responsibilities increase work-related stress among health workers					
11. High demands from different work department contribute to the prevalence of work-related stress.					
12. Insufficient opportunities to question supervisors about change at work can contribute to work-related stress.					
13. Work place bullying can contribute to the prevalence of work-related stress among health care workers.					
14. Interpersonal conflict among physicians and other health care workers can contribute to work-related stress.					
15. Workplace harassment in form of unkind words or behavior contribute to work-related stress?					
16. Traumatic events, such as work place death contributes to work-related stress?					

17. Lack of support through emotionally demanding work can contribute to work-related stress among health care workers.					
18. Lack of support from colleagues and your supervisor can increase work-related stress among health care workers.					
19. Inflexible work time increase the incidence of work-related stress.					
20. Tight deadlines contribute to work-related stress among health care workers.					
21. Long working hours contribute to work-related stress among health care workers.					
22. Heavy workloads contribute to work-related stress among health care workers.					
23. Neglect of some task due to high work demand increase work-related stress among health care workers.					
24. Uncooperative patients and their families can increase work related stress					
25. Unrealistic time pressure increase work-related stress.					
26. Uncertainties concerning patient treatment increase work related stress.					
27. Not having a choice in deciding your work speed increase work-related stress among health care workers.					
28. Not clear about what is expected of you at work can contribute to work related-stress.					

29. Not having a clue on how to get your job done increase work-related stress.					
30. Not been clear on the goals and objectives of your department increase work-related stress.					
31. Lack of understanding on how your job role fit into the overall aim of the organization increase work related stress .					
32. Negative working relationships with both colleagues and superiors increase work- related stress.					
33.Strained relationships at work increase work related stress.					
34. Instances of poor communication breakdown negatively affect work relationships.					
35. Frequent policy and procedure changes tend to increase work related stress.					
36.Coping with the pace of changes in the healthcare sector can be challenging.					
37.Lack of effective training by the organization when introducing changes increase work-related stress.					
38.When changes are made at work, uncertainties on how they will work out in practice increase work related stress.					
39.Not having a say on when to go on break increase work related stress.					
40. Not having a choice in how your work is done increase work related stress.					

41. Not having a say to some extent over the way you work, increase work related stress.					
42. Lack of supportive feedback on work done increase work related stress.					
43. Lack of employee support programs by the organization tend to increase work related stress.					
44. Lack of assistance from colleagues when the work gets difficult increase work related stress.					

Section C– Impact of work-related stress on service delivery in the healthcare sector

Item	Response				
	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)
45. Work-related stress affects the quality of service delivery in the healthcare sector.					
46. Work-related stress among healthcare workers has led to decreased attentiveness or concentration in service delivery.					
47. Work-related stress contributes to reduced productivity in service delivery.					
48. Work-related stress increases the likelihood of medical errors or mistakes in service delivery.					
49. Work related stress has an adverse impact on patient satisfaction with the healthcare services provided.					
50. Delays in service delivery can occur as a result of work-related stress among healthcare workers.					

51. Work-related stress contributes to increased absenteeism, affecting service delivery.					
52. Work-related stress hampers effective teamwork among healthcare professionals, impacting coordinated service delivery.					
53. Work-related stress may result in reduced patient trust and satisfaction with healthcare services.					
54. Work-related stress increases the likelihood of healthcare professionals seeking alternative employment.					
55. Implementation of enhanced support programs and resources can help alleviate work-related stress.					

QUALITATIVE QUESTIONNAIRE

Participant Information:

1. Participant Code:
2. Gender: Male Female
3. Age:
4. Position of Staff in the Hospital: _____
5. Specify your current hospital or research site: _____

Interview Schedule:

1. Date of your interview: _____

2. Time of interview: _____
3. Specify your department: _____

Themes Emanating from the Empirical Investigation:

Theme 1: Effects of Work Stress on Health Care Workers

1. How do you perceive stress affecting your decision-making and job performance?
2. In your experience, how does stress impact the quality of care provided to patients?
3. Can you share instances where stress compromised precision in your work (lab processes/medication dispensation)?

Theme 2: Causes of Stress Faced by Healthcare Workers

1. How does the workload and staffing levels in your workplace contribute to your stress?
2. Can you elaborate on how bureaucratic hurdles and resource constraints contribute to stress in your role?
3. How do interprofessional conflicts and the pressure to meet performance targets impact your stress levels?

Theme 3: Strategies for Dealing with Work Stress

1. Have you sought support within your team to cope with work-related stress? Can you share any experiences?
2. How have mindfulness practices and professional development programs helped you navigate work-related stress?
3. In your opinion, how important is maintaining a healthy work-life balance? What organizational support do you think would be beneficial in addressing work-related stress?

Appendix 3 – Ethical Clearance Form from the Health Research Ethics committee,
Federal Capital Territory.

FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY
Health Research Ethics Committee

Research Unit, Room 10 Block A Annex, HMSS, FCTA Secretariat,
No. 1 Kapital Street, Area 11, Garki, Abuja.

Notice of Research Approval

Approval Number: FHREC/2022/01/243/19 - 12 -22

Full Study Title: Prevalence of Work-Related Stress and its Determinants among Health Care Workers in Selected Health Care Facilities in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

Principal Investigator: Juliet Orunwebho

Address of Principal Investigator: Dept. of Public Health, Faculty of Basic and Applied Biological Sciences, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Kaduna

Date of receipt of valid application: 01/12/2022

The FCT Health Research Ethics Committee (FCT HREC) has approved the research described in the above stated protocol.

This approval is valid from **19/12/2022** to **18/12/2023**.

Note that no activity related to this study may be conducted outside of these dates. Only the FCT HREC approved informed consent forms may be used when written informed consent is required. They must carry FCT HREC assigned protocol approval number and duration of approval of the study. The FCT HREC reserves the right to conduct compliance visit to your research site without prior notification

The National Code of Health Research Ethics requires the investigator to comply with all guidelines, rules and regulations regarding the conduct of health research, and with the tenets of the code.

Modifications: Subsequent changes are not permitted in this research without prior approval by the FCT HREC.

Problems: All adverse events or unexpected side effects arising from this project must be reported promptly to FCT HREC.

Renewal: If this project is to proceed beyond the expiration date, an annual report should be submitted to FCT HREC early in order to request for a renewal of this approval.

Closure of Study: At the end of the project, a copy of the final report of the research should be forwarded to FCT HREC for record purposes, and to enable us close the project.

For further information, contact FCT HREC office. I wish you best of luck with your research.

Desmond Emereonyeokwe
Secretary, FCT HREC
December 19, 2022

**Appendix 4- Permission to administer Questionnaires from each of the general hospitals
(Wuse, Garki and Maitama general hospital)**

HEALTH AND HUMAN SERVICES SECRETARIAT
WUSE GENERAL HOSPITAL
CONAKRY STREET WUSE ZONE 3
P.M.B 24
FCDA, ABUJA

Our Ref: FCTA/IHSS/WDH/GEN/167
Your Ref:

Tel: 09-5232885
Date: 12/01/2023

Juliet Orunwebho
Principal Invigilator.
Department of public Health,
Ahamadu Bello Univerisity, Zaria.

**RE: REQUEST FOR PERMISSION TO ADMINISTER
QUESTIONAIRES**

I am directed to inform you that approval has been granted for you to carry out your research work Title '**Prevalence of Work-Related Stress and its Determinanats among Health Care Workers in Selected Facilities in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.**'

2. Kindly accept the assurances of Management esteem regards.

3. Wishing you success.

Abubakar M. U
For: Medical Director.

HEALTH AND HUMAN SERVICES SECRETARIAT, FCTA
MAITAMA DISTRICT HOSPITAL

E-mail: fmaitamadhb@yahoo.com

61 Aguiyi Irons Street, Maitama
P. M. B. 66,
FCTA, Abuja

08020871867
08125603937

Our Ref: *FCTA/HHS/HMB/GEN/038/T*

Date: *10th January 2023*

Juliet .O. Orunwebho
Ahmadu Bello University (ABU)
Zaria, Kaduna State

NOTICE OF RESEARCH APPROVAL

Sequel to your request to conduct a research in our hospital I wish to convey the approval of the Ethics and Research Committee for you to conduct a research on **"Prevalence of work-Related Stress and its Determinants among Health Care Workers in selected Health Care Facilities in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.** This approval is valid from 19/12/2022 to 18/12/2023.

2. Consequently, you are therefore expected to report to the HOU's in the various unit in the hospital for further instructions, please

3. Congratulations.

Mark O. Bassey
For: Chairman, Ethics & Research Committee

GHA/HR/GEN/0019/23

Juliet O Orunwebho
House 64, Valencia Estate,
Dakwo District
FCT
Abuja

Sir,

RE: REQUEST FOR PERMISSION TO ADMINISTER QUESTIONNAIRES

Your letter dated 11th January, 2023 on the above subject matter refers

Please be informed that Hospital Management has approved your request

Thank

EUME ABENE BENSON (MRS)
HEAD OF HUMAN RESOURCES
For: Medical Director

Cc: file

Tafawa Balewa Way, Area 3 Garki- Abuja

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Appendix 5 – Work Plan

Month Task	Dec- 2022	Jan- 2023	Feb- 2023	Mar- 2023	Apr- 2023	May- 2023	Jun- 2023	Jul- 2023	Aug- 2023	Sep- 2023	Oct- 2023	Nov- 2023	Dec- 2023
Ethical approval													
Literature review													
Data collection													
Data analysis													
Writing of first draft													
Editing													
Writing of final draft													
Presentation and submission													